

NOVEL MEASUREMENT SYSTEM FOR DETERMINING TEXTIL BEHAVIOR DURING OUT-OF-PLANE IMPREGNATION

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ABSTRACT

An out-of-plane permeability measurement system is presented that initially enables monitoring of inhomogeneous hydrodynamic compaction of textiles during impregnation. For this purpose, it provides linear variable differential transformers (LVDTs) in combination with ultrasonic technology, allowing continuous tracking of total stack compaction, flow front progression and single layer displacement. From this data the non-linear distribution of fiber volume content (V_F) along sample thickness can be derived. After final validation it can also be used for parameter studies regarding the influence of process- and material-related parameters on the processing behavior of technical textiles during liquid composite molding processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) processes, in which thermoset resin impregnates a dry, typically textile-based reinforcement structure, are widely used for industrial manufacturing of fiber reinforced polymer composites. For shell-like parts, i.e. with a large surface area in relation to thickness, out-of-plane impregnation can significantly reduce cycle times due to flow path length reduction. To optimize LCM processes, knowledge about textile permeability is crucial. Permeability describes conductance of a porous media for fluid flow and is defined by Darcy's law (1) for saturated flow [1]:

$$\vec{v} = -\frac{K}{\eta} \vec{\nabla} p \quad (1)$$

Here \vec{v} is the volume-averaged fluid velocity, $\vec{\nabla} p$ is the pressure gradient, η is the viscosity of the fluid and K is the permeability tensor of the porous media. The equation can be used for the unsaturated case, when flow front position $L(t)$, pressure gradient $\vec{\nabla} p(t)$ and the volume flow $Q(t)$ (all depending on time) is known, further the sample area A is also needed. For three-dimensional case, K is defined by a second order tensor, which is often reduced for textiles, assuming certain symmetry conditions:

- K_1 highest in-plane permeability
- K_2 lowest in-plane permeability
- K_3 out-of-plane permeability

Experimental determination of permeability is commonly done by impregnation (unsaturated flow) under controlled conditions regarding injection pressure or flow rate, while using a fluid with known viscosity. Flow front tracking allows deriving \vec{v} , and Darcy's law is then applied to calculate permeability. V_F strongly impacts permeability and therefore experiments are usually performed at specific levels of V_F . However, fluid flow can lead to textile deformation causing undefined deviations from the intended V_F . This is a challenge especially for transverse permeability measurements, where

the complete stack undergoes a complex hydrodynamic compaction, illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Complex hydrodynamic compaction of a stack of textile layers during transvers direction impregnation.

Initially, when fluid flows into the cavity, in which the textile stack is placed, the stack will be homogeneously compacted by fluid pressure. Simultaneously, impregnation begins. During the impregnation process there is a non-linear pressure gradient between fluid entering and flow front, which can be approximated by a combination of Darcy's law (1) with Terzaghi's principle (2) [2, 3]. Latter defines that for each infinitesimal element of the textile stack, effective compaction pressure acting on the textile p_{eff} is given by total pressure σ_{total} in pure fluid zone over the stack (= injection pressure), subtracted by fluid pressure p_{fluid} at the position of the layer.

$$\sigma_{total} = p_{eff} + p_{fluid} \quad (2)$$

Pressure drops over flow length due to flow resistance of textile and hence, compaction pressure increases to its maximum at flow front and is constant in dry preform area. Accordingly, V_F increases between fluid entry and flow front. This has been shown in experimental and simulative investigations e.g. by Klunker et al. [4]. Transverse permeability is quasi-exponentially correlated with V_F and will therefore be highly influenced in a way that it is decreased with increasing V_F [4]. This in turn affects fluid pressure evolution which again affects V_F etc., so at end there is a loop of interdependency. The time depending compaction behavior of the preform is mainly caused by viscous compaction response, which leads to this loop. The objective of the development leading to the new measurement system was not to bypass these effects during measurement as this is never fully possible, but to enable monitoring of all these effects under well-defined process conditions, as they occur in real-life processes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Figure 2 shows a photograph, CAD-model and schematic illustration of the novel measurement system that is supposed to fulfill the following requirements:

- Generation of an unsaturated flow at constant injection pressure up to 10 bar
- Defined initial V_F (cavity height)
- Continuous metrological determination of:
 - Pressure drop
 - Flow rate
 - Flow front progression
 - Total stack compaction (change of thickness of sample)
 - Single layer movement (reference layer for validation of V_F distribution) under saturated condition

As can be seen in Figure 2, the sample is positioned between two perforated aluminum discs acting as distribution media. A pressure vessel feeds the system with the test fluid and the flow rate is measured with a flow meter. As test fluid a rapeseed oil is used. Rapeseed oil is widely used as a test fluid for permeability measurements due to the comparable viscosity to standard resin systems. Furthermore, rapeseed oil is harmless for health and unproblematic to dispose. The test fluid is injected into the inlet chamber via four horizontal channels in order to impede a direct flow impulse on the sample. After the fluid has passed the sample and the upper distribution media, it flows into an outlet chamber, which in turn provides horizontal outlet channels to prevent backlog and minimize hydrostatic fluid pressure. The resulting actual pressure drop is monitored by pressure transducers positioned before the lower distribution media and above the upper distribution media.

Figure 2: Photograph (upper), CAD-model (lower left) and schematic illustration (lower right) of the measurement system.

Ultrasonic technology (through-transmission method) is used for continuous flow front monitoring. This approach, initially developed by Stöven et al. [5], exploits differences in speed of sound in dry and wet regions, leading to a decrease of time of flight of the ultrasound waves with progressing flow front. The measurement method and the set-up are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Measurement method and set-up of flow front tracking.

While the upper distribution media is fixed, the lower one is moveable and in permanent contact with spring-loaded linear LVDT. The spring rate of the three LVDTs in combination with three additional springs is designed so that the distribution media can follow the compaction of the fiber stack up to 1.25 mm. The spring force is just high enough to ensure permanent contact, but low enough to neglect the influence on the compaction. Furthermore, the LVDTs and springs are arranged symmetrically, to ensure a parallel movement of the distribution media without tilting. The contact points of the single LVDTs are in between the holes of the distribution media, to ensure that the areal impregnation is not disturbed. An illustration of the arrangement is shown in Figure 8. When hydrodynamic compaction occurs in an extent leading to total stack compaction (change of sample thickness), the lower distribution media will follow this movement.

Figure 4: CAD model of the total compaction monitoring technology.

For monitoring of single layer displacement, ultrasonic technology following impulse-echo method is applied. The method and set-up is shown in Figure 5. In this case, a single ultrasonic head is used as transmitter and receiver. A small metallic insert (currently aluminum foil, \varnothing 10 mm at a thickness of 0.025 mm) is placed between two layers, within the stack, and acts as hard reflecting material. At a hard reflection material, the biggest amount of the impacting ultrasound is reflected, allowing tracking of the movement when different injection pressures are applied. With knowledge of total compaction and insert displacement, the V_F distribution over the sample thickness can be approximated.

Figure 5: Measurement method and set-up for saturated single layer displacement tracking.

2.1 Sound-transmission through the measurement system

To track the flow front progression, the ultrasonic sound is emitted by the transmitter, then passes the insert in which the transmitter is mounted, followed by the distribution media, the sample itself and the insert in which the receiver is mounted (compare Figure 6). The inner inserts are necessary to protect

the ultrasonic heads against the testing and the cleaning fluid. The ultrasonic sound is eventually received on the other side of the measurements system by the receiver

Figure 6: Visualization of the ultrasound transmission and reflection.

The transmission through the measurement area is challenging, as every interface (change of the material) causes partial reflection, leading to a weakening of the sound. The amount of reflection can be calculated by the reflection coefficient (4) which is valid for vertical sonication [11].

$$R = \left(\frac{m-1}{m+1} \right)^2 \text{ with } m = \frac{\rho_1 \vartheta_1}{\rho_2 \vartheta_2} \quad (4)$$

Thereby, ρ_1 is the density and ϑ_1 the sound velocity of the material where the sound comes from and ρ_2 is the density and ϑ_2 the sound velocity of the material where the sound goes. Accordingly, the amount of reflection depends on the density and the sound velocity differences in the bordering materials. The bigger the difference of density and sound velocity, the bigger is the reflection.

This is illustrated in Table 1, where the reflection coefficients for selected material combinations have been calculated. Thereby, the sound velocity of a dry textile is anisotropic [13], comparable with the permeability or the mechanical properties of a textile. It also depends on the textile architecture and the fiber material. For this reason, an exact sound velocity of a certain dry textile has to be measured.

Table 1: Amount of reflection of the ultrasonic sound at the interface of different material combinations.

	<i>Rapeseed oil</i>	<i>Aluminum</i>	<i>PMMA</i> ¹	<i>Glass fiber</i>	<i>Carbon fiber</i>	<i>Air</i>
<i>Rapeseed oil</i>	-	73.6%	18.1%	0% - 6.8%	3.5% - 17.5%	99.9%
<i>Aluminum</i>		-	46.3%	74.1% - 83.5%	81.1 - 88.2%	99.9%
<i>PMMA</i> ¹			-	18.9% - 38.1%	32.3% - 51.3%	99.9%
<i>Glass fiber</i>				-	0.57% - 16.8%	>99.7%
<i>Carbon fiber</i>					-	>99.5%
<i>Air</i>						-
Material data:						
ρ in kg/cm ³	0.91 [9]	2.7	1.18 [10]	2.55 [10]	1.8 [10]	0.001293 ⁴ [11]
ϑ in m/s	1,432 ²	6,300 [6]	2,740 [6]	≈ 300 - 500 ³	≈ 300 - 500 ³	331 ⁴ [11]

¹ Polymethylmethacrylat

² Measured by IVW

³ Estimation by measurements by IVW

⁴ Normal air density and sound velocity

In addition to the reflection behavior at the interface of different material combinations for the construction, further material properties have to be considered. At the end, the best compromise between the different necessary properties is needed.

These are:

- Necessary mechanical properties for the use under measurement application
- Chemical resistance against test- and cleaning fluid
- Suitable ultrasonic behaviors, e.g. low inherent damping properties

Regarding the mechanical and chemical properties a metal would fit to the wanted material properties, e.g. aluminum. Furthermore, aluminum has a low inherent damping for sound, which would make it suitable for the wanted application. Regarding this point, aluminum would fit as construction material for the inner inserts and the distribution media. Becker et al. [12] have successfully used an aluminum distribution media for a similar application.

In the next step, the amount of reflection at the interfaces of the different material combinations is investigated. The first reflection is between lower inner insert for the ultrasonic head (transmitter) and the test fluid, the second between test fluid and lower distribution media, followed by the distribution media and textile, textile and test fluid (at partly saturated condition) and finally between textile and upper inner ultrasonic head insert (receiver). This already shows that the necessary build-up leads to a challenging measurement task. For this reason, the measurement system must provide high power, the interfaces must be reduced to the minimum and the reflections at the necessary interfaces must be minimized by intelligent material selection.

A closer look at Table 1 shows that the reflection at the surface between aluminum and rapeseed oil, as well as aluminum and textile, leads to a high reflection between 73.6% and 88.2%, which would lead to an error in the measurement with the available ultrasonic systems. Aluminum is for this reason not suitable as construction material for the inner inserts and the distribution media.

Regarding mechanical and chemical properties, polymethylmethacrylat (PMMA) is also suitable as construction material for the inner inserts. PMMA is a widely used material for ultrasonic applications due to the good permeability for ultrasound [6] with a T_g of around 106 °C [8]. It is for example used for ultrasonic-based weld seam testing and therefore its suitability for ultrasonic purposes is proven [6]. Hence, to reduce the amount of reflection, inner inserts are made out of PMMA, which reduce the reflection between inner insert and test fluid to 18.1% and the between textile and PMMA to 18.9% - 51.3% depending on the textile and the sound velocity in the textile.

A distribution media totally made out of PMMA is regarding the mechanical properties of PMMA not practicable. Due to the force of the compaction to the final FVC, the lower distribution media could bend or damaged. For this reason, a material combination between aluminum and PMMA is used. The main distribution media is made out of aluminum and just the transmission area, where the sound has to pass the lower distribution, is made out of PMMA. Therefore, they have been pressed and glued into the distribution media at the place where the sound mainly goes through the distribution media. Figure 7 shows the distribution media including the PMMA inserts.

Figure 7: Lower distribution media with PMMA inserts.

2.2 Sound-isolation

Monitoring of flow-front progression and single layer displacement are realized by exploiting ultrasonic technology. Thereby, it is the goal to transmit the sound through the textile. Nevertheless, if sound velocity between fluid / textile (e.g. rapeseed oil $\vartheta_{rapeseed\ oil} = 1,432\ m/s$ at $20^{\circ}C$ (measured by the IVW)) is compared with sound velocity in metal (e.g. aluminum $\vartheta_{aluminum} = 6,300\ m/s$ at $20^{\circ}C$ [6]), it can be seen that the sound velocity of metal is much higher. This can lead to a “bypassing problem”, i.e. the received sound signal is not the sound, which goes through the textile, but through the aluminum measurement cell. Therefore, to ensure proper measurement, this bypassing must be prevented. For this, two methods can be used:

1. The setup is designed in a way that the distance the sound waves have to propagate in the cell is so long that it arrives at the receiver after the sound waves propagating through the sample.
2. Damping elements are included, which sufficiently damp the bypassing signal.

Variation 1 is not practicable, due to the high differences in the speed of sound. For this reason, the second method has been chosen. An illustration of the build-up with a corresponding damping insert is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: CAD model of the arrangement of the insert for the ultrasonic head and the damping insert.

The design comprises two inserts. The inner one provides minimal damping, so that the sound waves are directed towards the ultrasonic head. The outer one provides high damping to minimize bypassing effects. It is important that both inserts can bear all mechanical stresses occurring during measurement. Hence, two materials with fairly good mechanical properties, but with different damping behavior, are needed. The inner one must have low damping properties to transmit as much sound as possible through the sample and the outer one must damp as much sound as possible to prevent bypassing effects. Polymeric materials were chosen to reach this goal. Generally, the damping behavior of a plastic is low under the glass transition temperature (T_g), increases with increasing temperature, has its maximum as the T_g and keeps the high level, which can be explained by improved movability of the polymer chains [7]. This leads to the results, that the material for the inner ultrasonic insert has to have a T_g above the operating temperature (room temperature) of the measurement system and the damping insert a T_g close under the operating temperature. The damping inserts are made out of polyoxymethylen (POM), which has a T_g around $-60^{\circ}C$, leading to a good damping behavior. Also mechanical properties and chemical resistance are sufficient [6]. Figure 9 shows the damping as well as the insert for the ultrasonic head as finished parts, separated and mounted.

Figure 9: Photos of the damping and ultrasonic head inserts.

2.3 Race-tracking preventing system

Prevention of race-tracking, i.e. unwanted flow at sample edges, is crucial for accurate permeability measurement. Hence, two different race-tracking preventing methods have been developed and tested (see Figure 10). First method provides a sealing of the edge area of the sample with a two component silicone prior to the testing. With this sealing a pure flow in out-of-plane direction is ensured. In the second method, an elastomer ring of elliptic shape, and an inside contour which is 1.5 mm bigger than the sample outer contour, is placed between case of the measurement system and sample (Figure 10, bottom, step 1). After compacting the sample to the final V_F (step 2), the elastomer ring is compressed (step 3), as a result of which the ring expands and seals the sample by shape adaption. An illustration of the single steps is shown in Figure 10. Both methods have been tested extensively and were proven to reliably prevent race-tracking.

Figure 10: Sample sealed with a two component silicone (left), pre-tests with an additional elastomer ring squeezed (right) and squeezing sealing procedure (lower).

3 VALIDATION AND RESULTS

The results of the validation tests are shown in Figure 11. To validate the accuracy of the impulse-echo method for single layer displacement, a validation test was performed in which movement of the lower distribution media is simultaneously tracked with LVDTs and ultrasonic (diagram ①). The results of ultrasonic are within standard deviation of the three LVDTs.

The second validation test (diagram ②) compares ultrasonic flow front monitoring with a theoretical calculation based on the flow meter results. For this, the flow front progression $L(t)$ is approximated based on injected volume over time $V(t)$, the total V_F and area of the sample A are needed (only valid if hydrodynamic compaction is negligible and V_F is fairly constant over thickness):

$$L(t) = \frac{V(t)}{A * (1 - V_F)} \quad (3)$$

The characteristics of progresses show good agreement up to the point where hydrodynamic compaction becomes significant and causes a fluid rich zone in the lower area.

The third validation test focused on monitoring total compaction and movement of an insert placed in the middle of the stack behind ply 15, depending on step-wise pressure increase (diagram ③a). Diagram ③b shows the movements relative to the initial position at 0 bar. If compaction was homogeneous, the movement of the first layer (LVDTs) should be twice as high as the movement of the middle layer (insert). As this is not the case, it proves inhomogeneous compaction resulting from relaxation at the first layers (in flow direction) and maximum compaction at the last layers. Furthermore, the single layer displacement shows a time-depending reaction behavior. Yet, for an exact textile behavior determination, further investigations with different textiles, V_F , pressure steps and amounts of layers must be carried out.

Figure 11: Results of validation tests.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The novel measurement system allows simultaneous tracking of the flow front progression and the total compaction during impregnation, as well as simultaneous single layer displacement and a total

compaction monitoring depending on injection pressure under saturated flow conditions. First validation tests performed with a woven glass fabric prove basic functionality. Further tests will follow to assure full functionality and to define limitation of use. After that it can be used for parameter studies with the objective to gain insights about the influence of process- and material-related parameters on the processing behavior of technical textiles during LCM.

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